

Perovskite QD in polymer for UV-sensitized silicon sensors: AFM-in-SEM analysis of morphology and charging landscape

Conversion of UV radiation is becoming increasingly important for sensors, detectors, catalysis or energy harvesting. Correlative AFM-in-SEM microscopy was used to analyze a novel device construction on the basis of a standard Si detector, where wavelength shifting mechanism from UV to visible is achieved by the luminescence effect of perovskite quantum dots embedded in polymer layers. AFM-in-SEM analysis can distinguish the layer topography, composition, and electrostatic charging landscape.

Figure 1: Correlative probe-electron image (CPEM) where SE grayscale intensity map is overlaid on 3D AFM topography of the spray-coated polymer layer with embedded CPB perovskite QD agglomerates.

Figure 2: Simultaneous acquisition of topographical, compositional and electronic information on the spray-coated polymer layer with the perovskite CPB QDs obtained by the CPEM method: a) atomic force microscopy image in self-sensing tapping mode, b) scanning electron microscopy image in secondary electrons regime.

AFM-in-SEM analysis shows that AFM topography and SEM image of the polymer layer with CPB perovskite QD (obtained in the same spot by the CPEM method) do not exhibit the same features. It is confirmed by the data correlation graph in Fig. 3. SEM thus reveals additional material and electronic information. The correlated 3D CPEM image in Fig.1 then overlays this information on the actual surface topography obtained by AFM. Thereby, CPEM provides full insight into the topography, composition and spatial charging of the CPB-polymer layer on the UV sensors.

No obvious trend in correlation of the SEM secondary electron intensity with the AFM surface topography (height) data in Fig. 3 suggests that the bright SEM features correspond to photoluminescent agglomerates of PCB QDs.

Figure 3: Correlation of the SEM secondary electron intensity with the AFM surface topography (height) data obtained from the CPEM method.

